

The Effect of Primary, Secondary and Tertier Economic Growth on Poverty and Their Relationship with Community Welfare of District/City in West Kalimantan Province

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ABSTRACT: In a development process occur obstacle as well as obstacle, so will result in development Becomes hampered, one that becomes blocker from success development a country is poverty. So that government area nor government center try for do countermeasures poverty through activity programs for reduce poverty.

Destination from study this is for test and analyze influence growth economy primary sector, sector secondary, sector tertiary to poverty as well as for test and analyze influence poverty to well-being public Regency/City In the province of West Kalimantan. Study this using secondary data during six year with method analysis use multiple linear regression with panel data and statistical tests. Research results showing that primary sector and sector secondary take effect negative and significant to poverty, while sector tertiary take effect positive and not significant as well as poverty take effect negative and significant to well-being public Regency/City In the province of West Kalimantan.

KEYWORDS: Poverty, Primary sector, Sector secondary, Sector Tertiary and Welfare Public.

INTRODUCTION

Economic development aim for reduce poverty, provider field work as well as cope inequality income and one the most important thing for describe success development economy that is enhancement quality source power human. Government programs for reduce poverty not yet showing optimal results because more many of these programs

prioritized on programs that are sector for that need there is the right strategy in cope poverty. West Kalimantan Province which has total the biggest poor. For that role government area in cope poverty really important to reduce level poverty. Following this is the data on the Poverty Rate Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province 2015 – 2020 as following.

Table 1: Poverty Level Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province 2015 – 2020 (Percent)

District ./ City	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Average
Sambas	9.42	8.54	8.59	8.55	8.19	7.7	8.50
Stuffed	6.94	7.46	7.51	7.17	6.96	6.62	7,11
Hedgehogs	13.51	12.32	12.23	11.77	11.47	11,12	12.07
Mempawah	5.52	5.75	5.94	5.61	5.32	4.95	5.52
Sanggau	4,57	4.51	4,52	4.67	4,57	4.46	4.55
Ketapang	11.72	10.99	11.02	10.93	10.54	10.29	10.92
Sintang	9.33	10.07	10.2	10.35	9.65	9.27	9.81
Kapuas Hulu	9.66	9.82	9.45	9.6	9.62	8.33	9.41
Sekadau	6.50	6.14	6.46	6.17	6,11	5.87	6,21
Melawi	12.57	12.63	12.54	12.83	12.38	12.04	12.42
Kayong Utara	9.84	10,19	9.89	10.08	9.98	9.56	9.92
Kubu Raya	5.22	5.04	5.26	5.07	4.74	4.42	4.96
Pontianak	5.22	5.55	5.31	5.00	4.88	4.7	5,11
Singkawang	5.76	5.33	5.42	5,12	4.91	4.53	4.22
West Kalimantan	8.03	7.87	7.88	7.77	7.49	7.17	7.70

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics West Kalimantan Province (Data processed).

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Poverty rate 2015-2020 Regency/City general every year experience drop will but drop the still very small. If seen from level poverty province so still many areas in the Regency/City which have level poverty above province that is Sambas Regency, District Hedgehog, Ketapang Regency, District Sintang, Kapuas Hulu Regency, Melawi Regency and North Kayong. In Thing this height poverty something area caused the more increase total population, unemployment continues increase and growth economy relatively stagnant. Whereas level low poverty under West Kalimantan Province is districts Bengkayang, Regency Mempawah, District Sanggau, District Sekadau, District Kubu Raya, Pontianak City and Singkawang City. So there is level relative poverty in the area low, hal this because in an area the existence capable development empower public with open field job. Poverty still becomes very complex and related problems with aspect social, economic, cultural and aspects other. Effort for get rid of poverty covers various aspect in life public where must conducted by continuous and integrated. For resolve problem poverty government area need for make right policy target. Government try for increase development for the sake of achieving welfare in society, so that from various activity development start directed towards development area, thing this because areas that have level

persistent poverty increase. Development in every area conducted by integrated and sustainable in accordance with priority of each region so that poverty keep going decreased. Growth economy often linked with development human being target in development. Growth economy close relation with goods and services produced. Growth will achieved through use source more power productive. Growth economy is policies and efforts aimed at for increase level life public as well as even distribution income community and expand field work and can resolve problem drop poverty. Growth economy achieved through use source more power productive, including power work, thing this produce income more per capita high. Growth economy will could achieved if economy experience production process improvement goods and services by keep going continuously various sector or activity economy society. Change structure economy will could create field profession for public so that poverty and unemployment will decreased. Change structural has share sector economy Becomes three part that is Growth economy primary sector, growth economy sector secondary and growth economy sector tertiary. Following this data about growth economy Regency/City primary sector in West Kalimantan Province 2015 – 2020.

Table 2: District/City Primary Sector Economic Growth in West Kalimantan Province– 2020 (Million Rupiah)

County /City	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sambas	11,226,271.63	11,813,974.13	12,411,928.95	13,023,675.16	13,643,137.73	13,367,732.04
Stuffed	4,649,502.81	4,880,159.76	5,163,899.18	5,434,858.36	5,714,396.52	5,600,474.14
Hedgehogs	5,763,419.04	6,067,561.36	6,381,212.22	6,694,979.23	7,022,179.06	6,975,267.37
Mempawah	4,175,723.34	4,425,719.6	4,685,371.26	4,955,360.48	5,241,754.13	5,251,537.46
Sanggau	11,047,183.54	11,636,867.84	12,157,876.57	12,670,003.8	13,163,333.5	13,255,682.66
Ketapang	13,529,100.04	14,607,934.98	15,661,142.01	16,887,779.26	18,022,027.56	17,932,651.06
Sintang	7,830,065.18.	8,243,737.69	8,683,369.95	9,130,727.07	9,588,496.01	9,378,535.08
Kapuas Hulu	5,301,109.3	5,580,747.19	5,881,743.05	6,155,951.73	6,392,680.57	6,237,506.65
Sekadau	3,432,929.76	3,636,659.73	3,848,258.07	4,072,437.48	4,294,373.83	4,252,448.46
Melawi	2,809,295.05	2,942,746.29	3,081,202,077	3,242,894.14	3,389,914.94	3,352,524.41
Kayong Utara	2,062,067.14	2,185,465.4	2,302,835.38	2,416,579.82	2,537,640.29	2,518,960.8
Kubu Raya	14,493,652.26	15,416,533.31	16,424,299,12	17,287,111.07	18,275,888.73	17,832,608.95
Pontianak	20,747,494.76	21,801,143.39	22,881,967.08	23,846,673.62	24,833,239.27	23,847,214.46
Singkawang	5,311,801.9	5,930,951.93	6,250,017,27	6,540,219.8	6,832,587.08	6,666,365.2

Source: Central body Statistics.

Growth economy District/City primary sector in West Kalimantan Province generally from 2015 – 2019 experienced increase but in 2020 generally District/City experiencing drop, only districts Mempawah and District Sanggau course in 2020 experiencing increase. Although growth economy primary sector in several District/City experiencing increase will but if seen from rate growth so could said growth economy all over District/City experiencing deceleration, this because existence change structural from transition power shift work from growth

economy primary sector shift to sector secondary and tertiary. The more decrease total power work so will result in output growth generated by the primary sector will experience sluggish growth and even will experience decline. Between growth economy primary sector and growth economy sector secondary have linkages one each other this because growth primary sector as provider ingredient raw for growth sector secondary. Following this data about growth economy sector secondary Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province in 2015 – 2020 as following.

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Table 3: Sector Economic Growth Secondary District/City Di West Kalimantan Province 2015 – 2020 (Million Rupiah)

County /City	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sambas	11,226,271.63	11,813,974.13	12,411,928.95	13,023,675.16	13,643,137.73	13,367,321.04
Bengkayang	4,649,502.81	4,889,159.76	5,163,899.18	5,434,858.36	5,714,396.52	5,600,474.14
Hedgehogs	5,763,419.04	6,067,561.36	6,381,212.22	6,694,979.23	7,022,179.06	6,975,267.37
Mempawah	4,175,723.34	4,425,719.6	4,685,371.26	4,955,360.48	5,241,754.13	5,251,537.46
Sanggau	11,047,183.54	11,636,867.84	12,157,876.57	12,670,003.8	13,163,333.5	13,255,682.66
Ketapang	13,529,100.04	14,607,934.98	15,661,142.01	16,887,779.26	18,022,027.56	17,932,651.06
Sintang	7,830,065.18	8,243,737.69	8,683,369.95	9,130,727.07	9,588,496.01	9,378,535.08
Kapuas Hulu	5,301,109.3	5,580,747.19	5,881,743.05	6,156,951.73	6,392,680.57	6,237,506.65
Sekadau	3,432,929.76	3,636,659.73	3,848,258.07	4,072,437.48	4,294,373.82	4,252,448.46
Melawi	2,809,295.05	2,942,746.29	3,081,202.07	3,242,894.14	3,389,914.94	3,352,524.41
Kayong Utara	2,062,067.14	2,185,465.4	2,302,835.38	2,416,579.82	2,537,640.92	2,518,960.8
Kubu Raya	14,493,652.26	15,416,533.31	16,424,299.12	17,287,111.07	18,275,888.73	17,832,608.95
Pontianak	20,747,494.76	21,801,143.39	22,881,967.08	23,846,673.62	24,833,239.27	23,847,214.46
Singkawang	5,311,801.9	5,930,951.93	6,250,017.27	6,540,219.8	6,832,587.08	6,666,365.2

Source: Central Agency Statistics

Growth economy sector secondary in general from 2015 – 2019 experienced increase every year, only in 2020 growth economy sector secondary district/city experiencing drop, thing this because exists in some area that has lateness in growth economy sector secondary and also difference investment that goes in every area, only a number of districts only experienced increase that is districts Mempawah and District Sanggau .

Growth sector secondary will could resolve poverty if activity production more character congested lots of work need power work, so will open field work, more many power employment absorbed in the sector secondary so causing income public increase so that poverty will experience decline. Growth

economy sector secondary also affected by growth sector tertiary in Thing this growth sector tertiary this appear because existence growth sector secondary in Thing this for promote results the production. With growth economy sector tertiary where activity production more character congested creation so that many need power automatic work will open field work.

Growth economy sector tertiary that can absorb power work more many so that will reduce number poverty and unemployment. Following this data about growth economy sector tertiary Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province in 2015 – 2020 as following.

Table 4: Sector Economic Growth Tertiary District / City Di West Kalimantan Province 2015 – 2020 (Million Rupiah)

County /City	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sambas	11,226,271.63	11,813,974.13	12,411,928.95	13,023,675.16	13,643,137.73	13,367,321.04
Bengkayang	4,649,502.63	4,889,159.13	5,163,899.18	5,434,858.36	5,714,396.52	5,600,474.04
Hedgehogs	5,763,419.04	6,067,561.36	6,381,212.22	6,694,979.23	7,022,179.06	6,975,267.37
Mempawah	4,175,723.34	4,425,719.6	4,685,371.26	4,955,360.48	5,241,754.13	5,251,537.46
Sanggau	11,047,183.54	11,636,867.84	12,157,876.57	12,670,003.8	13,163,333.5	13,255,682.66
Ketapang	13,529,100.04	14,607,934.98	15,661,142.01	16,887,779.26	18,022,027.56	17,932,651.06
Sintang	7,830,065.18	8,243,737.69	8,683,369.95	9,130,727.07	9,588,496.01	9,378,535.08
Kapuas Hulu	5,301,109.3	5,580,747.19	5,881,743.05	6,155,951.73	6,392,680.57	6,237,506.65
Sekadau	3,432,929.76	3,636,659.73	3,848,258.07	4,072,437.48	4,294,373.82	4,252,448.46
Melawi	2,808,295.05	2,942,746.29	3,081,202.07	3,242,894.14	3,389,914.94	3,352,524.41
Kayong Utara	2,062,067.14	2,185,465.4	2,302,835.38	2,416,579.82	2,537,640.92	2,518,960.8
Kubu Raya	14,493,652.26	15,416,533.31	16,424,299.12	17,287,111.07	18,275,888.73	17,832,608.95
Pontianak	20,747,494.76	21,801,143.39	22,881,967.08	23,846,673.62	24,833,239.27	23,847,214.46
Singkawang	5,311,801.9	5,930,951.93	6,250,017.27	6,540,219.8	6,832,587.08	6,666,365.2

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics.

Growth economy sector tertiary in general from 2015 – 2019 experienced increase every year, only in 2020 growth

economy sector tertiary district/city experiencing drop, thing this because exists in some area that has lateness in growth

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economy. Only a number of districts only experienced increase that is districts Mempawah and District Sanggau. This thing caused entry investment foreign so that right create field profession lots of new need power work. Growth economy sector tertiary for each region will different especially low quality growth economy sector tertiary because existence the factors that influence it. Growth sector tertiary will could resolve poverty if activity production more character congested lots of work need power work, so will open field work, more many power employment absorbed in the sector tertiary so causing income public increase so that poverty will experience drop With growth economy sector tertiary where activity production more character congested creation so that many need power automatic work will open field work. Growth economy sector tertiary that can absorb power work more many so that will reduce number poverty and unemployment. With thereby if rate growth an economy that doesn't accompanied with absorption power work so will result in poverty the more increase. Where is the economy in West Kalimantan Province? Growth his no could resolve poverty. Rate growth economy in West Kalimantan from 2015 – 2020 which is still relatively slow so will affect ability growth economy in reduce level poverty. Growth economy is important thing in something area, growth inclined economy

slow and still poverty high. Although level poverty experience drop will but drop still relatively small. For that effort must conducted government area in resolve poverty. Government as one executor development naturally need quality human as authorized capital development, for produce quality human need efforts for increase quality source power man that. Expenditure government aimed at for development human and also a reflection policy taken government. Expenditure government in Thing this for finance sector public and become priority in increase source power human who will reflected in the Human Development Index (IPM). Priority main in increase quality source power man is level higher education and health so that could determine ability for absorb and manage source development economy good in relation with technology for increase well-being resident. Human development put man as destination end from development no tool from development, success from development man could seen from how much big basic problem could overcome, as for the problem including poverty, unemployment, nutrition bad and blind letters. Various size for see development man between regions or between countries, namely with see Human Development Index (IPM).

Table 5: Human Development Index Regencies /Cities in West Kalimantan Province Year 2015 – 2020 (In Points)

District/ City	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sambas	64.14	64.94	65.92	66.61	67.02	67.03
Stuffed	64.65	65.45	65.99	66.85	65.57	67.87
Hedgehogs	64.12	65.58	64.93	65.45	65.96	65.98
Mempawah	63.37	63.84	64.00	64.9	65.5	65.74
Sanggau	63.05	63.9	64.61	65.15	65.67	65.77
Ketapang	64.03	64.74	65.71	66.41	67.16	67.17
Sintang	64.18	64.78	65.16	66.07	66.7	66.88
Kapuas Hulu	63.73	63.83	64.18	65.03	65.65	65.69
Sekadau	62.34	62.52	63.04	63.69	64.34	64.76
Melawi	63.78	64.25	64.43	65.05	65.54	65.55
Kayong Utara	60.09	60.87	61.52	61.82	62.66	62.68
Stronghold _	65.02	65.54	66.31	67.23	67.76	677.95
Pontianak	77.52	77.63	77.93	78.56	79.35	79.44
Singkawang	70.03	70.1	70.25	71.08	71.72	71.94
West Kalimantan	65.59	65,88	66.26	66.98	67.65	67.66

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics West Kalimantan Province.

By general average Index Development Human (IPM) Regency/City of West Kalimantan Province experienced increase every year even index development people of Pontianak City and Singkawang City more tall than the Province of West Kalimantan.

Human development put man as destination end from development no tool from development, success from development man could seen from how much big basic problem could overcome, as for the problem including

poverty, unemployment, nutrition bad and blind letters. Various size for see development man between regions or between countries, namely with see Human Development Index (HDI). Human Development Index (HDI) is used for classify is A country is a developed country, a developing country or underdeveloped countries and also for measure influence from policy economy to quality live. Human Development Index (HDI) becomes indicator urgent for measure success in effort build quality life humans who can

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explain results development with get income, health, and education.

LIBRARY REVIEW

Mirza (2012) Poverty is something state poor and helpless lucky, a minus state (deprivation), if entered in context certain, thing that related with the minimum income and wealth, weakness physical, isolation, fragility and helplessness.

Kuncoro (2010) that poverty divided Becomes three part namely:

- a. Poverty appear because dissimilarity pattern ownership that causes inequality distribution income.
- b. Poverty caused because source power possessed _ quality low so that causing productivity low and in the end wages received are also low.
- c. Poverty appear because existence difference in access to capital.

Kuncoro (2010) states poverty divided Becomes two part namely:

a. Absolute Poverty

Poverty absolute is residents who have well-being reflected low with not ability in fulfil all need life everyday so that are below the poverty line.

b. Poverty relatively

Relative poverty is not ability somebody in reach standard the life that has been determined by the community local because existence not even distribution income received by society.

Simon Kuznet in Budiono (1999) stated that growth economy is increase capacity in period long from the country concerned for provide various goods economy to its inhabitants. Ascension capacity that alone determined by the presence progress or adjustment technology, institutional (institutional) and ideology to various demands existing situation. That thing make growth economy characterized with three Thing tree among other:

- a. Rate growth per capita in the real sense (real).
- b. Spread or distribution force work according to sector activity production that becomes source his livelihood.
- c. Distribution pattern resident.

according to Budioo (1999) states that growth economy is one of the processes of increasing output per capita in period long where emphasis on three aspect Among other :

- a. Process that is growth economy no is something description from something the economy that sees how something economy develop or from time to time.
- b. Output per capita that is growth economy related with existence increase in output per capita in Thing this there is two important element such as total output and quantity resident.
- c. Period time that is increase in output per capita for 1-2 years then followed decrease in output per capita no is

growth economy. It says grow when in period long time (5 years or more) experience increase in output per capita.

Boediono (1999) stated that growth economy is a process of increasing capacity production in something economy by sustainable towards more well realized in form increase income national nor income area in period long.

Rostow in Kuncoro (2003) shared growth economy into five stages namely:

a. Economy Traditional

Economy public still character simple and way match plant still use method traditional. Use technology in activity production limited. At stage this the primary sector holds important role. Low benefit technology causing public only capable provide ingredient raw raw course, the social structure of society character tiered. Ability mastery source the available power is strongly influenced by the relationship kinship.

b. Pre Condition Stay take off

It is a transition process from society that relies on the primary sector towards sector based society secondary and tertiary. Sector secondary and tertiary growing in addition to the primary sector which is still have role urgent in economy. At stage this economy start move dynamic sector secondary and tertiary start emerging and developing technology has assist the production process.

c. Stay take off

At stage this occur revolution related industries with revolution method production used. At stage this investment productive range between 5-10 percent from income national. Development sector secondary namely the manufacturing sector have rate high growth. Presence by fast form from political, social and institutional triggers expansion modern sector (sector secondary and tertiary) and impact external capable push growth economy.

d. Going to Maturity

At stage this modern technology already applied by effective. At stage this occur three change urgent that is first power work already dominated by power work educated, second change character entrepreneur who at first worker hard and rough be a smooth and polite manager, third public already start experience saturation so that want more changes far again.

e. High Period Condition

At stage this occur migration by massive from center city to fringe city as impact from existence central the place work in the area urban. Use vehicle personal nor general is necessary. At stage this occur change from from the supply side approach becomes the demand side in the applied production system and causes shift behavior economy from dripping weight side production switch Becomes side consumption. At

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stage this well-being not only for individual but for public wide.

Jhingan (2016) is available two influential factors against growth economy that is factor economic and non economic.

As for the factors economy as the following:

a. Source Power Nature

Source power natural is part most important in growth economy that includes source power natural like fertility land, its location and arrangement and so on. With abundance source power natural so economy will grow with fast. As Lewis points out, people will use the wealth he has with the best and of course this different with people who don't have riches that.

b. Capital Accumulation

Factor Viewed production by physical could produced called as capital. If the factors of production experience enhancement so will have an impact on increasing the output produced so that add capital accumulation. Capital formation can be seen from two different side that is in one side capital accumulation shows request effective from consumers who play a role as user results production and the other side creates efficiency productive for future production. Capital formation required because for fulfil need rising society be marked with increase request public will goods results production.

c. Organization

Organization have linkages with factor production in something activity economy. Through organization could complete all something related with activity production such as capital, labor and help increase results production.

d. Progress Technology

Progress technology is factor urgent in increase growth economy. Because with existence updates in the field technology will could help increase performance labor, capital, factors production and save time in the production process.

e. Distribution work and production scale

Through distribution work so worker will could work more fast because he only make one type goods course. This thing will push productivity workers.

Whereas non economic factors as following:

a. Factor Social

Existence factor social and cultural will take effect to growth economy because existence western culture that brings reasoning and skepticism that instills spirit smoldering in Thing invention new in the end will bring up class new merchant with a lot total businessman or trader so will make goods and services will increase so that economy will experience growth.

b. Factor Man

Man is source available power push growth economy with fast if have knowledge and skills. In thing this education have role urgent in increase quality source power man so that in

increase quality source power man so that will push discoveries new capable increase growth economy.

c. Factor Politics and administration

Structure politics and administration weak government will hinder growth economy a country. One for example is existence corruption. In Thing this role capable government resolve problems faced in the country and encourage activity economy in order to walk with good.

Mankiw (2003) emphasizes about how is the growth process occur in economy with two sector namely:

a. Sector traditional

is sector rural excess subsystem resident and marked with marginal productivity of energy same work with zero, Lewis assumes that in the sector rural based Agriculture occur power surplus condition work (surplus labor) as something fact if part power work in the sector Agriculture drawn so so sector the no will lost the output. With existence transition power work from sector transition power work from sector Agriculture to the industrial and service sectors has make sector Agriculture or primary sector start decrease growth caused public more focuses on the wages offered by the sector secondary and tertiary. Increase field profession sector secondary and tertiary will push height income per capita.

b. Sector modern economy marked with level high productivity and become the place shelter power surplus work in the sector Agriculture with method transfer power work little by little from economy subsistence. The transfer process occurs power work consequence there is a surplus of energy work in the sector traditional, as well output growth and increase absorption power work in the modern sector. Happening diversion power work from sector Agriculture to industrial sector as well as growth power work in the modern sector is possible because existence expansion of output in the sector that.

Sukirno (2006) has share sector based on field businesses in Indonesia become three group namely:

a. Sector agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, fisheries and quarrying and mining including in primary sector.

b. Industry processing, electricity, gas, water and construction including in sector secondary.

c. Sector trading large, hotel, restaurant, transportation, communication, finance, rental, service companies and services other including in sector tertiary.

As for Sector economy there is three namely:

a. Growth economy primary sector

Primary sector consists from sector agriculture, plantation, forestry as well as results mining or excavation. The primary sector is a sector that immediately utilise without through processing more first. In developing countries the primary sector is commodity main in development economy Thing this because Indonesia is an agricultural country that is known part people working in the primary sector, namely sector agriculture. Industry the primary sector which was originally

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is part most important for development economy will but after there is a development process then the country Becomes go ahead, thing this will result in slowly the primary sector will abandoned.

b. Growth economy sector secondary

Sector secondary is sector as activity processing the resulting output from growth economy the primary sector needed by the community where goods shaped goods half finished and stuff so. As for the group sector this is sector industry, sector electricity, gas, clean water and sectors construction.

c. Growth economy sector tertiary

Sector tertiary in activities produce service from product final generated by sector secondary. While what is included in group sector tertiary is sector transportation, trade, services finance, and services other.

Todaro (2011) that well-being public relate positive with income per capita, meaning the more tall level income per capita public so will increase his well being, Namum well being have connection negative with poverty, more tall level poverty so tend will lower well-being public that. Growth economy urgent for maintain well-being the people, however growth no end from development human, Growth only one tools, more urgent is how growth economy used for repair capability human and how people use capability the for his welfare. Growth economy, development man really urgent in effort reduce level poverty. This thing because good education and health allow poor people for increase Mark his assets.

Tambunan (2000) Human Development Index (HDI) or known with term Human Development Index (HDI) is indicators used for measure one aspect related important with quality results development human, that is degrees development human. HDI is something index composition based on three indicator namely: (a). Health; (b) Education achieved; (c) Standard life.

Todaro (2011) Human Development Index (HDI) can be shared Becomes three category namely:

- 0.00 - 0.499 categorized development man low.
- 0.50 -.0.799 categorized development man medium.
- 0.80 – 1,000 categorized development man high.

There are three components Index development Human (IDH) that is lamanya live measured by hope live in the moment birth and level education measured by combination between numbers literate letters on the population adult (with weight two third) and the average school age (with weight third) and level a decent life measured by production per capita that has been customized

Todaro (2011) development human be found three the core value of the development that is made purpose main namely:

a. Adequacy

It means is ability for fulfil need base society in general like clothing, food board, health and safety. If one need the not yet fulfilled so will causing backwardness absolute.

b. Identity

That is when society able to be human completely. That is is the presence of encouragement from diri alone for forward, capable appreciate diri alone, for feel diri appropriate and worthy do or chasing something and so on.

c. Freedom from attitude serve

That is is ability for choose as listed in development man is independence human. Independence and freedom here interpreted as ability for stand up upright and independent so that no enslaved by the pursuit perspective Theory in life. Freedom here also means as freedom to teachings yan dogmatic.

METHOD

Method research used is method descriptive that is method used for describe analysis something results study but no used for make more conclusions wide (Sugiyono 2009: 21). Research results with use method descriptive quantitative results study processed and analyzed for taken conclusion with emphasize analysis on numerical data so that could know significant relationship on the variable that.

Data used in study this is secondary data in the form of panel data (combined data from Time series data) with cross section data), term time six year start 2015 to 2020. Source of data obtained from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) of West Kalimantan Province. The data processed with a computer through the economic view software program (E -views 9).

1. Multiple Linear Regression / Multiple Linear Regression

The model used in study this is as following:

$$Y_{it} = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + e$$

Where:

- Y = Poverty
b₀ = Constant / intercept
b₁, b₂, b₃ = Coefficient Regression
X₁ = Growth economy primary sector
X₂ = Growth economy sector secondary
X₃ = Growth economy sector tertiary
e = Error term

2. Regression / Regression Simple

$$Y_{it} = a + bx + e$$

Where:

- Y = Community Welfare / HDI
a = Constant / intercept
b = Coefficient Regression
X = Poverty
e = Error term

3. Statistics Test

a. t test

t test is used for see influence variable independent to variable dependent by Partial with level confidence 95%.

Criteria taking decision from testing this are:

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- When Probability > 0.05 then H₀ is accepted H₁ rejected
- When Probability < 0.05 then H₀ is rejected H₁ accepted

b. F Uji test

F test used for see influence variable independent by together (simultaneously) against variable dependent. With level confidence / confidence 95%.

Criteria taking decision from testing this are:

- When Probability > 0.05 then H₀ accepted H₁ rejected
- When Probability < 0.05 then H₀ rejected H₁ accepted

c. Coefficient Determination (R²)

Coefficient determination used for measure big influence from variable independent to the ups and downs variable

dependent. With coefficient determination could used for get information about how much far deep modeling ability explain variation variable dependent with range Mark between 0 to with 1. If the value of R² close to 1 then ability variable independent in give information or influence will the more fine and if R² value small mean ability variable independent in explain variation dependent very limited.

RESULTS

Multiple Linear Regression

Research results so got results Multiple Linear Regression as following:

Table 6. Estimation Results Multiple Linear Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Prob.
C	44,88389	0.0000
Primary Sector Economic Growth (X ₁)	-4.743803	0.0000
Secondary Economic Growth (X ₂)	-1.347089	0.0462
Tertiary Economic Growth (X ₃)	0.824366	0.6912

Source: E-Views Processed Data

Based on results Multiple Linear Regression so got equality regression as following:

$$Y = 44.88389 - 4.743803X_1 - 1.347089X_2 + 0.824366X_3$$

Regression Results Multiple Linear could explained as following:

a. Primary Sector Economic Growth (X₁)

Based on results study Mark coefficient growth economy primary sector is -4.743803, meaning if growth economy the primary sector experienced increase one percent so poverty will experience drop by 4.743803 percent with assumption growth economy sector secondary and growth economy sector tertiary fixed.

b. Sector Economic Growth Secondary (X₂)

Based on results study Mark coefficient growth economy sector secondary of -1.347089, it means if growth economy sector secondary experience increase one percent so poverty will experience drop by 1.34089 percent with

assumption growth economy primary sector and growth economy sector tertiary fixed.

c. Sector Economic Growth tertiary (X₃)

Based on results study Mark coefficient growth economy sector tertiary of 0.824366, it means if growth economy sector tertiary experience increase as big as one percent so poverty will experience increase by 0.824366 percent with assumption growth economy primary sector and growth economy sector secondary fixed.

Statistics Test

a. t test

T test is performed for test is growth economy primary sector, growth economy sector secondary and growth economy sector tertiary respectively Partial take effect to poverty Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province.

Following this could seen in the table following this is t test as following.

Table 7: t test

Variable	t - Statistics	Prob.	Decision
Primary Sector Economic Growth (X ₁)	-4,800636	0.0000	Significant
Sector Economic Growth Secondary (X ₂)	-2.739172	0.0462	Significant
Sector Economic Growth Tertiary (X ₃)	0.398914	0.6912	Not Significant

Source: E-Views Processed Data

Based on Table 7 can explained as following:

1. Primary Sector Economic Growth (X₁)

Based on results testing hypothesis obtained results that Primary Sector Economic Growth has an effect negative and significant to poverty Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province.

2. Sector Economic Growth Secondary (X₂)

Based on results testing hypothesis obtained results that growth economy sector secondary take effect negative and significant to poverty Regency /City in West Kalimantan Province.

3. Sector Economic Growth Tertiary (X₃)

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Based on results testing hypothesis obtained results that growth economy sector tertiary take effect positive and not significant to poverty Regency /City in West Kalimantan Province.

b. F Uji test

Test done for knowing is growth economy primary sector, growth economy sector secondary and growth economy sector tertiary take effect by simultaneously or simultaneous to poverty Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province. Based on results calculation got F - Statistic value is 381,45778 with probability of 0.000000 p this mean that growth economy primary sector, growth economy sector secondary and growth economy sector tertiary by together

(simultaneously) influential _ _ significant to poverty Regency /City in West Kalimantan Province.

c. Coefficient Test Determination (R²)

Based on results study Mark coefficient determination (R²) is 0.986549 which means of 98.6549% of variable growth economy primary sector, growth economy sector secondary and growth economy sector tertiary capable explain the effect to poverty Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province, the remaining 1.3451% is influenced by other factors outside study this.

1. Regression / Regression Simple

Based on results study Linear Regression / Regression Simple so obtained results as following:

Table 8: Estimation Results Linear Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Prob.
C	26,64538	0.0000
Poverty (X)	-0.281345	0.0001

Source: Processed Data E-views

Calculation result could explained as following:

a. constant (C)

Based on results study Mark coefficient constant of 26, 64538 means if poverty no experience change so well-being public by 26.64538 percent.

b. Poverty (X)

Based on results study Mark coefficient poverty of -0.281345 means if poverty experience increase one percent so well-being public will experience drop by 0.281345 percent.

4. Statistic Test

a. Test t

Testing this done for test what poverty influential against well -being society /IPM. This thing can seen in the Table following this:

Table 9: t test

Vaiable	t-Statistics	Prob.	Decision
Poverty	-4.28049	0.0001	Significant

Source: E-Views Processed Data

Poverty (X)

Based on results testing hypothesis obtained results that poverty take effect negative and significant to well-being public Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province.

c. Coefficient Test determination (R²)

For measure big contribution / donation of the independent variable to the rise and fall of the dependent variable so result of 0.168779 means of 16.8779% of variable poverty capable explain the effect to well-being public Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province, the remaining 83.1221% is influenced by other factors outside study this.

Influence Primary Sector Economic Growth Against Poverty Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province.

Growth economy influential primary sector negative and significant to poverty Regency/City in West Kalimantan

Province. This is caused if growth output economy primary score generated experience increase so will impact on the increase in absorption power work so that poverty will experience decline. Growth economy sector primary has ability in resolve level poverty in West Kalimantan Province, p this could showed based on absorption power work. In the primary sector in absorb power work more many compared to from another sector. So that will could absorb power work more many and potential reduce unemployment and poverty. With thereby so chance work will open wide as well as given convenience in work in the primary sector. If seen from the data then absorption power work primary sector still dominates in West Kalimantan, the primary sector remains Becomes source main income _ for part of society big work in the primary sector. This thing could seen in the table following this.

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Table 10: Workers Working in Main Sectors in West Kalimantan Province 2015 – 2020 (people)

Sector	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Primary	1,313,719	1,163,519	1,227,995	1.231.775	1,209,394	1,292,582
Secondary	233.248	273.754	281,695	307,401	307,425	300,046
Tertiary	616,334	850,550	793,508	807,705	852.196	865,668

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS).

Primary sector every year fluctuate, year on year 2017 to In 2019, the primary sector experienced drop, thing this is because existence transformation structural displacement power work to sector secondary and sector tertiary. However fixed primary sector still becomes sector main part big working in the primary sector as source income people in West Kalimantan. Meanwhile, sector secondary and sector tertiary every year experience increase in West Kalimantan Province, p this because existence displacement profession from primary sector to sector secondary and sector tertiary. In the primary sector remains must developed so that could increase well-being public through the resulting output so that many need power great job, thing this result in drop level poverty. The more increase goods produced from primary sector then will capable push output increase, moreover total population experience increase every year so that cause need

will goods Becomes more increase. With the more increase request public so will could push the output so that will need power more work many for primary sector. With the more increase primary sector in West Kalimantan and occurred change structure in Thing this cause public beautiful profession from primary sector to sector secondary and sector tertiary because wages offered more big from sector primary, then will result in decrease in output primary sector. If in the primary sector experienced drop keep going continuously total power work so will impact on availability primary product no will fulfilled in West Kalimantan, hal this due to the resulting output the primary sector experienced drop as a result total power work also decreases, productivity power work relatively low with thereby well-being society also experiences drop so that poverty increase. Following this data about total power work in the sector main.

Table 11: Number of Manpower Working in the Main Sector (Soul)

Year	Labor _ No. Educated Primary Sector	Labor _ No. Educated Sector Seconds	Labor _ Not Educated Sector Tertiary	Labor _ Educated Primary Sector	Labor _ Educated Sector Secondary	Labor _ Educated Sector Tertiary
2013	1.132.150	128,360	258,568	135,949	52.605	346.191
2014	1.225.158	142.624	265.658	145.437	62.980	384.653
2015	1.167.508	151.503	274.470	146.211	81.745	341.864
2016	1.013.735	199.894	384.572	149.784	73.860	465.978
2017	1.071.545	188.327	314.439	156.450	93.368.	479.069
2018	1.060.199	214.808	311.389	171.576	92,593	396,316

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics (Data processed)

Labor no educated for primary sector every year experience drop from from 2013 to 2016, in 2017 the primary sector experienced increase and fall in 2018 again power work no educated primary sector. This thing because existence transformation structure economy move power work from primary sector to sector secondary and sector tertiary. For power work no educated sector secondary from 2013 – 2016 experienced increase every year and year 2017 energy work no educated sector secondary experience decreased and 2018 went up again power work sector secondary. Whereas for power work no educated sector tertiary from year 2013–2016 every year experience increase, and in 2017 – 2018 energy work sector tertiary experience decline.

Primary sector is not the greatest educated total power work vs sector secondary and sector tertiar. In sector no educated still dominated primary sector. Whereas power work no

educated in the sector secondary still belong to larger who work in the sector secondary no educated, for sector tertiary more many power work work on power work educated. Whereas power work educated working in the primary sector of year 2013 – 2018 every year experiencing increase, thing this mean power work educated primary sector still dominated by the primary sector and still required by energy work educated for work in the primary sector so that the sector could resolve level poverty. Workers who work in the sector secondary educated from year 2013 – 2015 every year experience increase whereas 2016 happened drop power work educated and in 2017 energy work educated sector secondary experience rise and fall return power work educated sector secondary in 2018. Growth economy where is the primary sector? growth experience deceleration, this is because activity production still character traditional, for that

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government need mix hand for address it in the primary sector in Thing this source power human who needs upgraded as well as use technology on activity production for increase output as well for increase productivity worker so that level poverty will reduced. Expected primary sector could Becomes mainstay in West Kalimantan because could increase income and energy work so that productivity work must also increase. With development the primary sector which is producer ingredient raw for sector secondary and sector tertiary as well as provider ingredient food for society that has been this the primary sector becomes source eye livelihood public so that could reduce unemployment as well as reduce level poverty. For that need mix hand government in develop primary sector use push more economy good again. The need increase source power man and use technology that has been this still use traditional, for build primary sector in the District/City in the province of West Kalimantan.

With increase productivity power work so will result in increase in primary sector output then will result in unemployment and rate poverty will down.

Influence Sector Economic Growth Secondary to Poverty Regencies /Cities in West Kalimantan Province

Sector secondary take effect negative and significant to poverty regencies/cities in West Kalimantan Province. This thing because with increase sector secondary so will result in poverty decrease Regency/ City in West Kalimantan Province. In sector secondary where many need ingredient obtained standard from primary sector for necessity production in the sector secondary. Growth economy sector secondary increase so will result in growth economy the primary sector will also increase hal this because primary sector as provider ingredient raw for necessity activity production sector secondary and sector tertiary so that income people who work in the primary sector in general will increase so that unemployment and rate poverty will also tend down. With growth economy sector secondary that can push growth economy sector tertiary in activities required by the sector secondary among other things, needs sector secondary the marketing and services and others. For necessity that 's a lot need power work so automatic will open field job. This thing will causing expansion chance future work _ will entered by workers so that unemployment reduced and level poverty will also reduced income society will also increase. Growth economy sector secondary in West Kalimantan in resolve poverty with road expand the effort that could open field wide range of work for people who haven't work. Contribution sector secondary in relative output formation small so that power work is also relative small will but if sector secondary growth keep going increase so with alone will capable open field profession for public so that number unemployment and numbers poverty will down. Sector

secondary no could resolve poverty in period long, hal this is because sector secondary not yet could absorb power a lot of work, because in production process use technology although occur expansion business sector secondary, will but only part small only able _ absorbed in the sector secondary. In use technology for the production process so need power work that has skills so that later with easy could apply all technology, for that required educated personnel so that they can apply technology. If seen from Table 4.6 which is a lot work in the sector secondary part big power work work in the sector secondary no educated compared to with power work educated. This thing due to sector secondary no educated no Requires a high education diploma work in the sector secondary no educated have low education _ they only work in the sector construction because no need level higher education so that power work sector secondary no educated more many power work compared to with power work sector secondary educated. Role government area in cope poverty with even distribution development in the sector secondary district/city in West Kalimantan Province. Even distribution development sector secondary must be in a developing area, no only in areas that have proceed so that occur even distribution in development sector secondary. If it happens even distribution at each area so will occur enhancement output growth that requires power work so that income public increase result in unemployment and poverty reduced. Because of that even distribution sector secondary schools in West Kalimantan Province will push sector tertiary and primary sectors in even distribution development in every area with thereby by no live could lower level poverty because opened field a lot of work needed by society so that will reduce level unemployment .

Influence Sector Economic Growth Tertiary to Poverty Regency /City in West Kalimantan Province.

Sector tertiary take effect positive and not significant to poverty Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province. This is because _ growth economy sector tertiary for work in the sector tertiary must have expected high education skills and diplomas will produce high productivity in work. However quality source power man still very low once, thing this seen from Table 4.6 where power work sector tertiary total power work still dominated sector tertiary no educated in West Kalimantan Province In the sector tertiary use technology is also needed no only sector secondary only need technology but sector tertiary also requires technology for productivity increase. For that required power work sector tertiary educated because that required source power capable human _ apply technology in order to walk with efficient and effective in activity production so that the resulting output increase. West Kalimantan province mostly have power work no educated so that ability as well as skill is also low, thing this will result in entry power foreign for working in West

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Kalimantan. In a growing economy develop as well as technology is also developing so that source power human who quality have ability as well as Skills so that could apply technology in activity production. Although power foreigners working in the sector tertiary in West Kalimantan still belong to small will but step beginning for power work foreign for permanent working in West Kalimantan. With absorbed power work foreigners working in the sector tertiary automatic will reduce chance power work local will work in the sector tertiary. Besides because presence of workers foreign, then energy happens work originating from outside West Kalimantan so that power work local will also reduced. Because of the many power work in the area _ for go to city in look for jobs in West Kalimantan. Sector tertiary growing in the area urban so that many power work originating from area come for look for work in West Kalimantan because level wages offered more big difference level wages Among area that has forward and area develop Thing this caused difference activity economy, productivity as well as difference cost live. The city of Pontianak as area already proceed where for reduce number poverty with method open field work more many compared to with area develop so that occur inequality between area in development result in income public no equally so that poverty the more increase. Role government area in resolve inequality really urgent for that policy government in resolve inequality so that chance work in the sector tertiary no only on area already proceed just will but push on all areas in development economy area. So that could attract investors to could invest in West Kalimantan, especially in the regions. Enter investment in the sector tertiary in various area so expected capable for open field work, energy work local more take precedence in enter field work in the area the so that unemployment as well as poverty will reduced.

Influence Poverty to District /City Community Welfare in West Kalimantan Province.

Poverty take effect negative and significant to well-being public Regency /City in West Kalimantan Province. In Thing this poverty is very influential to well-being community/Index development man if poverty increase so will result in well-being community/index development man down, where in Thing circle poverty there is three indicator that is education, health and power buy not capable achieved poor people with inability public in fulfil need so will could influence low quality source power human. Low his level health so will trigger happening poverty because level health low society will because productivity is also low. Productivity rate low will result in income low, with income low so result in poverty, with poverty causing somebody no capable for maintenance health as well as education. Based on Thing the poverty is very influential to index development human, if poverty down so will result in index development

man increase. In circle poverty there is three indicator development man that is health, education and power buy not _ capable achieved by the poor. not ability for fulfil need the will impact on the low quality source power human. Low number poverty in the region that, thing this caused area the capable reduce number poverty so that will impact on index development human, with many opened field profession so that need power work. In something circle poverty there is three axis the main cause somebody to be poor that is low level health, low level education and low level income. The Human Development Index (HDI) includes three Thing that is age long, healthy, knowledgeable and a decent life. Age healthy length _ could be measured number hope live on a area, the more tall number hope life so will result in health public the more good so that impact on productivity work. Productivity work increase so will increase income that has an impact on the decline level poverty. On dimension knowledge could seen from Expected length of school and average length of school if walk with good so will raise quality society. Quality source power humans go up then public capable in produce goods and services so that impact on income public so that will lower level poverty.

Life worthy could seen from expenditure per capital, in Thing this if in something area of average expenditure per capita tall so could describe power buy society is also high, with income public tall so result in down number poverty. Poor people in West Kalimantan Province tend to showing drop Thing this because existence enhancement in well-being society. In Thing this government West Kalimantan Province focus in push number poverty although not yet reach target as expected will but number poverty from 2016 to 2020 continues experience decline. In Thing this government area expected could push growth economy more local productive for increase well-being society. Well-being public increase so could seen from down level poverty. Role government really urgent especially in increase development, in advance and develop the area so government area given authority for organize and manage the area alone

CONCLUSION

Growth economy influential primary sector negative and significant to poverty Districts/Cities in West Kalimantan Province. This thing because primary sector more many absorb power work so that will reduce unemployment and poverty. For working in the primary sector is not need level higher education, so that level society education low will working in the primary sector, as eye his livelihood.

Growth economy sector secondary take effect negative and significant to poverty Regency / City in the province of West Kalimantan. This thing because sector secondary in cope poverty with open business new a lot need power work automatic will open field wide range of work for people who haven't work so that will reduce unemployment and poverty.

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Growth economy sector tertiary take effect positive and not make it clear to poverty Regency /City in West Kalimantan Province. This thing because sector tertiary need abilities and skills for apply technology as well as requires a high education diploma whereas source power available human _ quality low so that need power work foreign for could apply technology.

Poverty take effect negative and significant to well-being community/ Human Development Index (HDI) Regency/City in West Kalimantan Province. This is because poverty is very influential to well-being community/index development human, if poverty down so will result in index development man increase, In circle poverty there is three indicator development man that is health, education and power buy what you do n't capable achieved by the poor. Inability for fulfil need the will impact on the low quality source power human.

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